

54th Days of Preventive Medicine International Congress

27-30. September 2022.
Niš, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

Public Health Institute Niš

Faculty of Medicine,
University of Niš

Serbian Medical Society

Niš, 2022.

*122 years of Public Health Protection in Serbia
from regular preventive activities
to great challenges in COVID-19 pandemic time*

*122 године заштите јавног здравља у Србији
од редовних превентивних активности
до великих изазова у време пандемије COVID-19*

**PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE NIŠ
FACULTY OF MEDICINE, UNIVERSITY OF NIŠ
SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY, NIŠ**

**54TH DAYS OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE
INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS**

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Editor in Chief

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Publisher

Издавач

Public Health Institute Niš - Институт за јавно здравље Ниш

Faculty of Medicine Niš, University of Niš - Медицински факултет у Нишу, Универзитет у Нишу

Serbian Medical Society - Српско лекарско друштво

For publisher

Prof. dr Miodrag Stojanović

All abstracts are published in the book of abstracts in the form in which they were submitted by the authors, who are responsible for their content.

The continuing education program number 10 A-11229/20 was accredited by the decision of the Health Council of the Republic of Serbia No. 153-02-00473/2020-01 from 21th May 2020.

ISBN 978-86-6265-111-2

MAIN TOPICS

- **Environment and health**
- **Nutrition and health**
- **Microbiology today**
- **Current parasitosis**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of communicable diseases**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of non-communicable diseases**
- **Health promotion – challenges and solutions**
- **Preventive aspect of healthcare organization**
- **Application of information and communication tools in the health care system**

The Congress is accredited (153-02-00473/2020-01 from 21th May 2020; number 10 A-11229/20) as international by the Health Council of the Republic of Serbia with the following number of points:

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19. PUPILS HABITS AND KNOWLEDGE RELATED TO PROPER DIET

Bjelanović J^{1, 2}, Koprivica M¹, Jevtić M^{1, 2}, Popović M^{1, 2}, Velicki R^{1, 2}, Bijelović S^{1, 2}, Dragić N^{1, 2}

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Objectives: Taking into account data from previous researches on the percentage of malnourished children, a this research was planned to determine the habits and knowledge of pupils about the principles of proper nutrition.

Methods: The research was conducted during 2019 and 2020 in four elementary schools in the municipality of Novi Sad. The data collected were based on a questionnaire created for the purposes of this research, on a sample of 118 first grade students.

Results: Analyzed survey data showed that a significant percentage of students do not have sufficient knowledge about the principles of proper nutrition, as well as its importance for health maintenance and disease prevention. More important, the students' answers related to eating habits point to the fact that milk, fresh fruits and vegetables are insufficiently included in their daily diet, while, on the other hand, snacks, sweets and, especially carbonated drinks, are present in the diet almost every day.

Conclusion: Inadequate habits and insufficient knowledge of students lead to the need for systemic problem solving, primarily by involving parents and schools, as well as local communities.

Keywords: diet, nutrition, schoolchildren, habits, knowledge